

Assessment of body image dissatisfaction and risk of developing eating disorder among undergraduate medical students

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ABSTRACT

Background: Body image dissatisfaction is one's own negative perception of their own body often caused due to wrongful ideation of ideal body image standards. Body image dissatisfaction may be linked to developing risk of eating disorders. The high prevalence of risk of developing eating disorders might hamper the normal functioning of the individual as a whole and his or her contribution to the society .

Objectives: To determine the prevalence of body image dissatisfaction and risk of developing eating disorder among undergraduate medical students. To assess the association between body image dissatisfaction and risk of developing eating disorder among undergraduate medical students.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted among medical under-graduate students in a medical college in Trichy district of Tamil Nadu . A total of 480 participants participated in this study A pre validated semi- structured, self - administered questionnaire consisting of three parts, including demographic details ,body image dissatisfaction using Stunkard's silhouette and Body shape questionnaire (BSQ-8C) and Eating attitude test -26 (EAT-26) for assessment of prevalence of risk of developing eating disorder was used.

Results: A total of 480 undergraduate medical students were included in the study with 40.8% Male and 59.2% female students. About 70.8% of the medical students were not satisfied with their body image and 43.9% of the students had mild to marked concern for body shape .The prevalence of risk of developing eating disorder among undergraduate medical students in 6.9%. There is significant association between risk of developing eating disorder and body image dissatisfaction.

Conclusion: In order to prevent eating disorders early screening and fostering healthy body image perceptions by adopting healthier lifestyle practices are necessary .

Key words: Body image dissatisfaction, Eating- disorder, medical students , Body shape , Mental Health

INTRODUCTION

The ideal standards of how a human body is perceived to appear ideally has been constantly changing over a period of time. It has been used to estimate the wealth of the nation indirectly in the past , for example in the past centuries the voluminous body was considered ideal and represented a wealthy population. From the various definitions of body image given in the previous literatures we can sum up that it's an individual's perception of once own body , but in broader terms it is influenced by many factors such as physical , psychological, socio-cultural factors and much more. Body image is seen as a relevant etiological factor in causing eating disorders ([1],[2]).

Body image dissatisfaction relates to negative evaluation of one's own body image and is often seen as a perceived discrepancy between a person's evaluation of his or her body and his or her ideal body perception [3].The body image dissatisfaction may prevail in varying intensity and impact the individual in various ways including eating disorders that may affect their quality of life [4],[5].

Nowadays one can see individuals ranging from severe thinness to morbid obesity in India and the trend is growing with each year. The main influence of these trends tend to be happening due to peer influence, wrong ideation of perfect body image, reduced physical activity, sedentary work and behaviour, and decreased attitude and knowledge regarding perfect health. Eating disorders are defined as deviations in eating behaviour which includes bulimia nervosa, anorexia and other non-specific disorders(6). There are various studies conducted across university students including students related to health sector reporting prevalence of risk of developing eating disorder [7],[8]. Medical profession on the whole is a rather tedious profession. The medical students in their journey of pursuing their profession undergo many stressful situations and time constraints. The situations worsen due to wrongful ideation of body image causing high prevalence of body image dissatisfaction and eventually lead to risk of developing eating disorders. Though eating disorder is a mental health condition the influence and impact of it on so many other factors make the overall health of the medical student low at an individual level and would eventually hamper their availability and dependability on their medical services in their future [8]. There are fewer studies in India, conducted among medical students aimed to find the prevalence of eating disorders and its association with body image dissatisfaction. Henceforth, the objective of this study is to determine the prevalence of body image dissatisfaction and risk of developing eating disorder among undergraduate medical students, and to assess the association between body image dissatisfaction and risk of developing eating disorder.

Materials and Methods :

Study design : Observational study - Cross Sectional Analytical Study

Study Population and Area: Under-graduate medical students studying from first year to final year in a medical college in the Trichy district of Tamil Nadu.

Sample size calculation : Early study by Dr.Abhilasha Kapoor et al (2023)[9] shown that prevalence of risk of developing ED among college students is 13.9%. Presuming similar observation to be made in this study by allowing 15% relative error with 95% CI the sample size calculated using the formula $n = Z^2_{1-\alpha/2} pq / d^2$ is 1092. Since the target population is around 700. By applying finite population correction, the required sample size is 430. Expecting around 10% non-response and refusal the sample size was calculated to be 480.

Inclusion criteria : Under-graduate medical students of a Medical College who consent to participate in this study will be included.

Exclusion criteria: Students not willing to participate in this study and not present at the time of study will be excluded.

Recruitment process: The sample size of 480 undergraduate students was selected by stratified random sampling with proportional allocation. According to which it was calculated as 172 students among 1st year, 109 students for 2nd year, 102 students for 3rd year and 97 students among the final year.

Questionnaire

A pre validated semi- structured, self - administered questionnaire consisting of three parts, Part -A consists of demographic details and Part-B consists of assessment of body image dissatisfaction using Stunkard's silhouette [10] with Cronbach's alpha value of (0.85) and Body shape questionnaire (BSQ-8C) [11] with Cronbach's alpha value of (0.91) and Part-C consists of Eating attitude test -26 (EAT-26) [12] with Cronbach's alpha value of (0.90) for assessment of prevalence of risk of developing eating disorder. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee Ref.No:786/TSRMMCH&RC/ME-1/2023- IEC No: 046 and study was conducted among the undergraduate medical students after acquiring permission from the concerned authority of the institution.

Body image dissatisfaction (BID) using Stunkard's silhouette :

The Stunkard silhouette consists of 9 silhouette figures that increase in size from very thin (value 1 to very obese having highest value 9 (Stunkard et al., 1983). The participant has to answer to the 2 questions given regarding their perceived current body image and perceived ideal body image. The final body image value was calculated by subtracting the values of the current body image and the ideal body image. Score of zero indicates satisfaction with current body shape, negative score (≤ -1) indicates the desire to become heavier and positive score ($\geq +1$) indicates the desire to become thinner.

Body shape questionnaire -8C (BSQ):

The BSQ is a measure of the body shape preoccupation . In the 8 item questionnaire the scores are determined on a 6-point scale ranging from 'always' to 'never', with 6 points allotted to 'always', 5 points to 'very often', 4 points to 'often', 3 points to 'sometimes', 2 points to 'Rarely 'and 1 point to 'never'. The total score ranges between 8 and 48. Score <19 indicate no concern, 19 to 25 as mild concern ,26 to 33 as moderate concern and >33 as marked concern for body shape.

Eating Attitudes Test – 26 (EAT-26) :-

The EAT-26 questionnaire is used widely for screening of eating disorders and it consists of three subscales namely Dieting; Bulimia and Food Preoccupation; and Oral control . It is a 26 item questionnaire and the questions from 1-25 are valued on a scale ranging from 'always' to 'never', with 3 points allotted to 'always', 2 points to 'usually', 1 point to 'often', 0 points to 'sometimes', 'rarely' and 'never' and 26th question is scored as 3 points to 'never', 2 points to 'rarely', 1 point to sometimes and 0 points to 'always', 'usually', 'often'. Participants with a composite score of ≥ 20 indicate behaviour and a tendency for disordered eating, and a risk for developing Eating Disorder.

Statistical Analysis :

Data entry was done in Microsoft Excel and analysis was carried out using statistical package SPSS IBM version 26.0. Descriptive measures such as mean and standard deviation were calculated for normally distributed data. Chi-square test was used to find out the association between demographic variables and Body image dissatisfaction , risk of developing eating disorders . For all statistical tests, a two-sided probability of $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

Results :

A total of 480 Medical students were included in the study . Table I shows distribution of the study participants according to the demographic data collected .It shows that about only 29.2% of the medical students were satisfied with their body image according to the BID score and according to BSQ scoring 43.9% of the students had mild to marked concern for body shape .The prevalence of risk of developing eating disorder among undergraduate medical students in 6.9%.

In Table II there is significant association between gender , year of study with the BID score and in Table III and age of the participant and year of the study shows significant association with the BSQ score .There is no significant association noted with EAT score and demographic characteristics according to Table IV. According to Figure 1 140 participants were satisfied with their body image and had no risk of developing eating disorder and it was found to be statistically significant($p=0.000$) .Similarly in Figure2 there is a significant association between body shape concern and risk of development of eating disorder ($p=0.000$).

TABLE I : SHOWS THE DEMOGRAPHIC DATA AND THE SCORES OBTAINED BY THE STUDY PARTICIPANTS (N=480)

CHARACTERISTICS	CATEGORY	FREQUENCY n(%)
Gender	Male	196 (40.8)
	Female	284 (59.2)
Age	<20 YEARS	187(39)
	>20 YEARS	293(61)
Year of study	1 st year	172(35.8)
	2 nd year	109(22.7)
	3 rd year	102(21.3)
	4 th year	97(20.2)
SCORES		
BIDS(Body image dissatisfaction)	Satisfactory with body image	140(29.2)
	Desire to become thin	231(48.1)
	Desire to become heavy	109(22.7)
BSQ (Body shape questionnaire)	No concern for body shape	269(56.1)
	Mild concern for body shape	113(23.5)
	Moderate concern for body shape	64(13.3)
	Marked concern for body shape	34(7.1)
EAT Score (Eating attitude test)	Risk of developing eating disorder	33(6.9)
	No risk of developing eating disorder	447(93.1)

TABLE II: ASSOCIATION OF BIDS SCORE AND DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PARTICIPANTS (n= 480).

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS	BIDS SCORE			P VALUE
	SATISFIED WITH THE BODY IMAGE n(%)	DESIRE TO BECOME THIN n(%)	DESIRE TO BECOME HEAVY n(%)	
GENDER	140(29.2)	231(48.1)	109(22.7)	
MALE	51 (36.4)	86(37.2)	59(54.1)	0.006
FEMALE	89(63.6)	145(62.8)	50(45.9)	
AGE				
<20 YEARS	61(43.6)	81(35.1)	45(41.3)	0.226
>20 YEARS	79(56.4)	150(64.9)	64(58.7)	
YEAR OF STUDY				
1 ST YEAR	61(43.6)	76(32.9)	35(32.1)	0.002
2 ND YEAR	33(23.6)	46(19.9)	30(27.5)	
3 RD YEAR	13(9.2)	61(26.4)	28(25.7)	
4 TH YEAR	33(23.6)	48(20.8)	16(14.7)	

TABLE III: ASSOCIATION OF BSQ SCORE AND DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PARTICIPANTS (n= 480).

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS	BSQ SCORE				P VALUE
	NO CONCERN FOR BODY SHAPE n(%)	MILD CONCERN FOR BODY SHAPE n(%)	MODERATE CONCERN FOR BODY SHAPE n(%)	MARKED CONCERN FOR BODY SHAPE n(%)	
GENDER	269(56.1)	113(23.5)	64(13.3)	34(7.1)	
MALE	114(42.4)	48(42.5)	23(35.9)	11(32.4)	0.564
FEMALE	155(57.6)	65(57.5)	41(64.1)	23(67.6)	
AGE					
<20 YEARS	118(43.9)	39(34.5)	14(21.9)	16(47.1)	0.006
>20 YEARS	151(56.1)	74(65.5)	50(78.1)	18(52.9)	
YEAR OF STUDY					
1 ST YEAR	106(39.4)	39(34.5)	15(23.4)	12(35.3)	0.04
2 ND YEAR	66(24.6)	21(18.6)	14(21.9)	8(23.5)	
3 RD YEAR	42(15.6)	30(26.6)	19(29.7)	11(32.4)	
4 TH YEAR	55(20.4)	23(20.3)	16(25)	3(8.8)	

TABLE IV: ASSOCIATION OF EAT SCORE AND DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PARTICIPANTS (n= 480).

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS	EAT SCORE		P VALUE
	AT RISK OF DEVELOPING EATING DISORDER n(%)	NOT AT RISK OF DEVELOPING EATING DISORDER n(%)	
GENDER	33(6.9)	447(93.1)	
MALE	16(48.5)	180(40.3)	0.354
FEMALE	17(51.6)	267(59.7)	
AGE			
<20 YEARS	12(36.4)	175(39.1)	0.751
>20 YEARS	21(63.6)	272(60.9)	
YEAR OF STUDY			
1 ST YEAR	10(30.3)	162(36.3)	0.399
2 ND YEAR	10(30.3)	99(22.1)	
3 RD YEAR	9(27.3)	93(20.8)	
4 TH YEAR	4(12.1)	93(20.8)	

FIGURE 1 : BODY IMAGE DISSATISFACTION AND RISK OF DEVELOPMENT OF EATING DISORDER

FIGURE 2: BODY SHAPE CONCERN AND RISK OF DEVELOPMENT OF EATING DISORDER

Discussion :

Growing importance on physical attractiveness and existing unrealistic ideologies of one's own body image has created more chaos than progress. A negative body image can lead to restricted or other disordered eating behaviours and increase the risk of developing eating disorders .In our study the prevalence of body image dissatisfaction among undergraduate medical students is 70.8%.In another a study conducted among university students through annual online survey analysis from 2017-2022 the prevalence of body dissatisfaction was found to be ranging from 63.5-71.7 % when calculated for each year [13].

A study conducted in the region of Murcia showed that about 61.2 % of the study participants were not satisfied with their body image which is similar to our study but was conducted among 3-18 year old children [14].The prevalence of body shape concern among the undergraduate medical students in our study was 43.9% including mild to marked concern for body shape .In a study conducted in Kerala among medical college students the prevalence of having concern on their body shape was noted to be 38.1% and a significant association with the risk of eating disorder and body shape concern was attained [15].In an another study conducted among medical students of southern Kerala about 18% of the students were found to have body image concerns and concluded that about one-fifth of their study participants have moderate to severe body image dissatisfaction[16].

It was determined that individuals having higher concern about their weight control had increased likelihood of engaging in weight control behaviours that are unhealthy and leading to a greater risk of developing eating disorder[17].In the same study conducted in Kerala the prevalence of developing eating disorder was found to be 19.1% [15]. which is considerably higher than our study where it is 6.9%.Body dissatisfaction is associated with disordered eating behaviours was found in a study done among college students among four provinces in china [18].This similarly correlates with the result of our study having positive association between body image dissatisfaction and risk of developing eating disorders.

Conclusion :

Our study shows a considerable amount of body image dissatisfaction among medical college students. Although there is lesser percentage of undergraduate students noted for developing the risk of having eating disorders , one cannot bypass the impact it may create in future . To prevent eating disorders screening of the risk factors may be carried out especially among the young age group that may help to device appropriate measures to counteract the problems involved .This also creates a need to foster healthy body image perceptions among the medical fraternity as a whole as they are the future professionals and influencers of the healthcare of our society.

Limitations :

As the current study is a cross sectional study and was conducted in a single medical college the findings of the study cannot be generalized to a larger population and cause effect relationship couldn't be studied. Social desirability bias is inherent issue in this study. More influencing factors that creates the risk of developing eating disorders can be included in future studies .

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